

Some Novel Alkoxy Chemistry of Rhodium(I)

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In contrast to the ready hydrolysability of transition metal alkoxides, the alkoxy and phenoxy bridged binuclear derivatives of rhodium(I) of the general formula, $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OR})]_2$ (COD=1,5-cyclooctadiene; $\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{CH}_2\text{CF}_3$, and Ph) can be synthesised by treating $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_2$ with NaOH/KOR in ROH-THF medium. The alcoholysis reactions of these alkoxides show interesting variations. A number of mononuclear rhodium(I) complexes $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{R}_1\text{COGHCOR}_2)]$ ($\text{R}_1=\text{R}_2=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}_1=\text{Ph}, \text{R}_2=\text{Me}$; and $\text{R}_1=\text{R}_2=\text{Ph}$) have been synthesised from the methoxy bridged binuclear rhodium(I) complex $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$.

In spite of considerable amount of work published¹⁻⁵ on the alkoxy derivatives of most elements of the periodic table during the last three decades, the alkoxy chemistry of later 3d, 4d and 5d elements has not been much explored. Work has been initiated on simple and bimetallic alkoxides of later 3d metals in our laboratories⁶ and on molybdenum and tungsten at Indiana^{6,7}.

Only the methoxy binuclear rhodium(I) complex $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ containing 1,5-cyclooctadiene has been fully characterised so far⁸⁻¹⁰, including its crystal structure¹¹. Rhodium complexes catalyse¹² the hydrogen transfer from Me_2CHOH to cyclohexene or acetophenone. However, the highest yields were obtained when $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ was used in the presence of Schiff bases 1 or 2.

In view of the above, it was considered of interest to extend our studies on the alkoxy derivatives of platinum metals. The present paper deals with the isolation of alkoxy and phenoxy rhodium complexes and a number of mononuclear rhodium(I) complexes $[(\text{COD})\text{RhL}]$ (L=anion of the β -diketones).

Experimental

Materials: $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_2$ was prepared by the reaction of $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with ethanol in the presence of 1,5-cyclooctadiene and analysed before use (Found: C, 39.4; H 4.8. $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_2$ calcd. for: C, 39.1; H 4.9).

Synthesis of alkoxy derivatives of Rh^{I} : The reactions of $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_2$ and NaOH/KOR ($\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5, \text{CH}_2\text{CF}_3$ and Ph) in 1:2 molar

ratio were carried out in ROH-THF medium. The contents were stirred and colour of the solution changed from orange to yellow. After removing the volatile solvents under reduced pressure, the products were extracted by dichloromethane to remove NaCl/KCl formed during the reaction. The products (yellow solids) were crystallised ($\sim 75\%$) in presence of regulated amounts of dichloromethane and parent alcohol. The details of their syntheses are presented in Table 1.

Exchange reactions: The exchange reactions of $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ with ethanol, n-propanol, n-butanol and t-butanol were carried out. Alcohol (~ 10 ml) was added to the solution of $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ in CH_2Cl_2 . The contents were stirred for about 24 h. The volatile fraction was removed under reduced pressure. The process was repeated to complete the reaction. The products were crystallised in CH_2Cl_2 -n-hexane medium. The details of these derivatives are given in Table 2.

Synthesis of β -diketonate derivatives of Rh^{I} : 2,4-Pentanedione, benzoylacetone or dibenzoylmethane (LH) in dichloromethane was added to a clear solution of rhodium complex $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ in dichloromethane. The contents were stirred for ~ 24 h to complete the reaction. The volatile solvent was removed under vacuum and the yellow products were crystallised in CH_2Cl_2 -n-hexane mixture (3-4 ml) at -10° . The details of their syntheses are recorded in Table 3.

Analytical methods and physical measurements: Carbon and hydrogen were determined by a Coleman 33 instrument. Infrared spectra (CsI) were recorded in the region $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using a Perkin-Elmer 577 grating spectrophotometer. ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) were recorded by Perkin-Elmer R12B at 60 MHz and R32B at 90 MHz Spectrometers using SiMe_4 as internal standard.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of bridged chlororhodium(I) complex $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_2$ (a) with NaOH/KOR in 1:2 molar ratio in ROH-THF medium ($\text{R}=\text{CH}_3, \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ or

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3$ WITH NaOH/KOR IN TETRAHYDROFURAN-PARENT ALCOHOL

Sl. no.	Reactants	Molar ratio and medium	Product	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				C	H
1.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + \text{NaOH}$ (0.78 g) (0.12 g)	1 : 2 Methanol + THF	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3$ Yellow pellets*	43.87 (44.60)	5.89 (6.20)
2.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + \text{NaOH}$ (0.68 g) (0.10 g)	1 : 2 Ethanol + THF	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OEt})]_3$ Yellow crystalline solid*	45.49 (46.85)	6.78 (6.64)
3.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + \text{NaOH}$ (0.42 g) (0.08 g)	1 : 2 2,2,2-Trifluoroethanol + THF	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CF}_3)]_3$ Dark yellow crystalline solid*	38.70 (38.42)	4.50 (5.53)
4.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + \text{K}$ (0.69 g) (0.11 g)	1 : 2 Methanol + THF	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3$ Yellow pellets*	44.03 (44.60)	6.44 (6.20)
5.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + \text{K}$ (0.35 g) (0.05 g)	1 : 2 Ethanol + THF	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OEt})]_3$ Yellow crystalline solid*	46.19 (46.85)	7.11 (6.64)
6.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + \text{NaOH}$ (0.60 g) (0.24 g)	1 : 5 Methanol + water (pH = 10-12)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OH})]_3$ Yellow crystalline solid*	41.72 (42.10)	5.95 (5.70)
7.	$[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_3 + 2\text{K}$ (0.54 g) (0.09 g)	1 : 2 Phenol + THF	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OPh})]_3$ Dark yellow crystalline solid**	54.79 (55.26)	5.99 (5.59)

* Soluble in CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 . ** Insoluble in CHCl_3 , CCl_4 .

TABLE 2—EXCHANGE REACTIONS

Sl. no.	Reactants	Product	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
			C	H
1.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{EtOH}$ (0.56 g) (excess)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OEt})]_3$ Yellow crystalline solid*	45.85 (46.85)	6.19 (6.64)
2.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{Pr}^n\text{OH}$ (0.48 g) (excess)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OPr}^n)]_3$ Yellow solid*	48.05 (48.88)	6.04 (7.03)
3.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{Bu}^n\text{OH}$ (0.52 g) (excess)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OBu}^n)]_3$ Dull yellow solid*	49.44 (50.70)	6.57 (7.39)
4.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{Bu}^t\text{OH}$ (0.44 g) (excess)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OBu}^t)]_3$ Yellow solid*	49.67 (50.70)	7.87 (7.39)
5.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OH})]_3 + \text{MeOH}$ (0.49 g) (excess)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3$ Yellow pellets*	43.88 (44.60)	6.46 (6.20)
6.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)]_3 + \text{MeOH}$ (0.41 g) (excess)	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3$ Yellow pellets*	44.13 (44.60)	6.06 (6.20)

* Soluble in CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 .

TABLE 3—REACTIONS OF $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3$ WITH β -DIKETONES IN DICHLOROMETHANE

Sl. no.	Reactants	Molar ratio and medium	Products	Analyses % : Found/(Calcd.)	
				C	H
1.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{acacOH}$ (0.42 g) (0.18 g)	1 : 2 CH_2Cl_2	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rhacac}]$ Yellow solid*	49.33 (50.30)	7.12 (6.13)
2.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{bzacH}$ (0.52 g) (0.34 g)	1 : 2 CH_2Cl_2	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{bzac})]$ Yellow solid*	57.77 (58.06)	5.78 (5.64)
3.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_3 + \text{dbmH}$ (0.48 g) (0.45 g)	1 : 2 CH_2Cl_2	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{dbm})]$ Yellow solid*	63.32 (63.59)	5.30 (5.30)

* Soluble in CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 .

CH_2CF_3) were carried out at room temperature and presented in Scheme 1. The reactions leading to the formation of bridged binuclear methoxo(b), ethoxo (c), fluorinated ethoxo(d) and phenoxo(e) rhodium(I) complexes were found to be light to dark yellow crystalline solids and soluble in dichloromethane and chloroform except complex (e) followed by the separation of NaCl/KCl after mixing and stirring of

the reactants. In these derivatives, the central rhodium atom is expected to have four-coordination environment as reported earlier⁸⁻¹⁰.

These alkoxo derivatives of rhodium exhibit some novel features in the chemistry of alkoxides¹ as a whole. Most of the transition metal alkoxides are hydrolysed irreversibly by even traces of moisture.

The $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OR})]_2$ derivatives can, on the other hand, be prepared in dilute alkaline solutions. Further, the hydroxy complex $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OH})]_2$ (f) synthesised by anion-exchange reaction of complex $[(\text{COD})\text{RhCl}]_2$ (a) at pH 10-12 is converted to the methoxo derivatives of rhodium(b) by an alcoholysis reaction.

The inter conversions between the complex (b) and (c) can also be carried out successfully by alcoholysis reaction. However, attempts to prepare branched/longer chain alkoxy derivatives using the anion-exchange method led to extensive decomposition; this may be ascribed to a facile β -hydrogen elimination process. But these derivatives (g-i) were successfully synthesised from the methoxo complex (b) $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ by treating with the corresponding alcohol under mild conditions. The resulting alkoxy derivatives of rhodium(I) are dull yellow solids and soluble in dichloromethane and chloroform.

Scheme 1

Further reactions of $[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$ with β -diketones, *i.e.* 2,4-pentanedione, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane were carried out, yielding

the corresponding mononuclear β -diketonates of rhodium(I) $[(\text{COD})\text{RhL}]$ complexes (j-l),

(L = anion of β -diketone; L for (j) = acac, (k) = bzac, and (l) = dbm.

Infrared spectra : A strong band is observed at $\sim 1075 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and this is a characteristic absorption band of the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ modes. In the case of complex (a), no band is observed in this region.

The metal-oxygen stretching bands in the resulting derivatives are observed in the region $560\text{--}590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. As compared to alkoxy derivatives, the Rh-O bond absorption for the phenoxo derivative is obtained at a relatively higher region (590 cm^{-1}). This shows the strengthening of the Rh-O bond due to mesomeric effect of the phenyl ring. The $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ for the phenoxo derivative also shows +ve shift appearing at 1240 cm^{-1} as compared to $\sim 1075 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the alkoxy derivatives.

In the β -diketonate rhodium complexes, the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ vibrations are observed around $1530\text{--}1550$ and $1560\text{--}1585 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. The mesomeric effect of the phenyl group in dibenzoylmethane complex is evident considering the lowering of the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ stretching vibrations as compared to benzoylacetone complex^{1,2}. Similar frequency shift is also observed for $\nu_{\text{Rh-O}}$ vibrations, *i.e.* a positive shift in dibenzoylmethane complex. This shows that the complex formed is tetraordinated with the O,O'-coordination of β -diketone anions.

^1H nmr spectra : In the ^1H nmr spectra, the olefinic and saturated protons appear in the region δ 3.25-4.25 and 1.2-2.7, respectively. The signals for cyclooctadiene protons are complex but the total

 TABLE 4— ^1H nmr SPECTRAL DATA FOR RHODIUM(I) COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Product	Olefinic protons δ	Saturated protons δ	Other protons δ	
1.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OMe})]_2$	3.6 (br s)	1.5-1.8 (m), 2.3-2.6 (m)	2.7 (s)	(OCH ₃)
2.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OEt})]_2$	3.5 (br s)	1.3-1.7 (m), 2.2-2.6 (m)	1.1 (t)	(OCH ₂ , OH ₂)
3.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CF}_3)]_2$	3.5 (br s)	1.3-1.7 (m), 2.4-2.8 (m)	2.9 (s)	(OCH ₂ , OH ₂)
4.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OH})]_2$	3.6 (br s)	1.6-1.7 (m), 2.30-2.7 (m)		
5.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OPr}^n)]_2$	3.8 (br s)	1.2-1.8 (m), 2.1-2.5 (m)	3.3-3.4 (t) 0.8-0.9 (t)	(OCH ₂) (CH ₂)
6.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OBu}^n)]_2$	3.5 (br s)	1.2-2.4 (m)	3.1 (t) 0.7-0.9 (t)	(OCH ₂) (OH ₂)
7.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{OBu}^t)]_2$	3.6 (br s)	1.2-2.1 (m), 2.1-2.7 (m)	1.25 (s)	(OH ₂)
8.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{acac})]$	4.0 (br s)	2.2 (m), 1.15-1.7 (m)	5.11 (s) 1.95 (s)	(acac-H) (acac-Me)
9.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{bzac})]$	4.0 (br s)	2.35 (m), 1.3-1.85 (m)	1.95 (s) 5.85 (s)	(bzac-Me) (bzac-H)
10.	$[(\text{COD})\text{Rh}(\text{dbm})]$	4.25 (br s)	2.5 (m), 1.4-1.95 (m)	7.25 (br s) 6.65 (s) 7.4 (br s) 7.8 (br s)	(bzac-Ph) (dbm-H) (dbm-Ph)

number of olefinic protons and protons on the saturated carbon atoms were found in the ratio 4 : 8. Resonances due to alkoxo protons are indicated in Table 4.

In the β -diketonate complexes the signals in the regions δ 5.10-6.68, 1.95 and 7.25-7.8 are assigned to the methine, methyl and phenyl protons, respectively, and no band is observed at δ 2.7 for methoxo group. This shows that the protic bidentate ligands (*i.e.* β -diketones) rupture the methoxo bridges to form mononuclear derivatives. The signal due to the methine group of the chelate ring is sensitive to the nature of the different substituents in β -diketones. The position of the signal is shifted towards higher region replacing methyl by a phenyl group. This is in accordance with the earlier observations of Bonati and Ugo¹⁴ in the nmr spectra of the dicarbonyl derivatives of rhodium(I) β -diketonates.

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